

**NINETEENTH YOUNG RESEARCHERS' CONFERENCE
MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING**

December 1-3, 2021, Belgrade, Serbia

Program and the Book of Abstracts

**Materials Research Society of Serbia
&
Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA**

2021

Book title:

Nineteenth Young Researchers' Conference - Materials Science and Engineering:
Program and the Book of Abstracts

Publisher:

Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA
Knez Mihailova 35/IV, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia
Tel: +381-11-2636994, 2185263, <http://www.itn.sanu.ac.rs>

Conference organizers:

Materials Research Society of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia
Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

Editor:

Dr. Smilja Marković

Technical Editor:

Aleksandra Stojičić

Cover page: Aleksandra Stojičić and Milica Ševkušić

Cover: Milica Ševkušić

Printing:

Gama digital centar
Autoput No. 6, 11070 Belgrade, Serbia
Tel: +381-11-6306992, 6306962
<http://www.gdc.rs>

Publication year: 2021

Print-run:

120 copies

CIP - Каталогизacija у публикацији
Народна библиотека Србије, Београд
66.017/.018(048)

YOUNG Researchers Conference Materials Sciences and Engineering (19 ; 2021 ; Beograd)

Program ; and the Book of abstracts / Nineteenth Young Researchers' Conference Materials
Science and Engineering, December 1-3, 2021, Belgrade, Serbia ; [organized by] Materials Research
Society of Serbia & Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA ; [editor Smilja Marković]. - Belgrade :
Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, 2021 (Belgrade : Gama digital centar). - XVIII, 86 str. : ilustr.
; 23 cm

Tiraž 120. - Registar.

ISBN 978-86-80321-36-3

а) Наука о материјалима -- Апстракти б) Технички материјали -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 51231241

Aim of the Conference

Main aim of the conference is to enable young researchers (post-graduate, master or doctoral student, or a PhD holder younger than 35) working in the field of materials science and engineering, to meet their colleagues and exchange experiences about their research.

Topics

Biomaterials
Environmental science
Materials for high-technology applications
Materials for new generation solar cells
Nanostructured materials
New synthesis and processing methods
Theoretical modelling of materials

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Results of the Conference

Beside printed «Program and the Book of Abstracts», which is disseminated to all conference participants, selected and awarded peer-reviewed papers will be published in journal “Tehnika – Novi Materijali”. The best presented papers, suggested by Session Chairpersons and selected by Awards Committee, will be proclaimed at the Closing Ceremony. Part of the award is free-of-charge conference fee at YUCOMAT 2022.

Sponsors

ANALYSIS
LABORATORY EQUIPMENT

Acknowledgement

The editor and the publisher of the Book of abstracts are grateful to the Ministry of Education, Sciences and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia for its financial support of this book and The Nineteenth Young Researchers' Conference - Materials Sciences and Engineering, held in Belgrade, Serbia.

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Development of a physiologically relevant 3D *in vitro* model for osteosarcoma cell cultivation comprising alginate composite scaffolds and a perfusion bioreactor system

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Osteosarcoma is the most common type of bone cancer, which affects both children and adults. Treatment of osteosarcoma exhibits slow progress due to inadequacy of both *in vivo* animal models and 2D *in vitro* models regularly used for antitumor drug testing. Our approach is to create a physiologically relevant 3D *in vitro* model for osteosarcoma cell cultivation, which has the potential to overcome inherent weaknesses of 2D *in vitro* and animal models. In order to imitate native osteosarcoma microenvironment, macroporous alginate scaffolds with incorporated hydroxyapatite/ β -tricalcium phosphate (HAp/ β -TCP) powder were produced with two compositions: 1 wt% alginate, 1 wt% powder and 2 wt.% alginate, 2 wt% powder. Bioactivity and stability of the scaffolds were investigated under biomimetic conditions of continuous flow of the culture medium in perfusion bioreactor at the superficial medium velocity of 400 $\mu\text{m/s}$, which was reported in literature to be beneficial for osteogenesis. Scaffolds with the higher alginate concentration was shown to be more stable in the culture medium, since the scaffolds with the lower alginate concentration disintegrated after 5-7 days under flow conditions. Biocompatibility of the obtained scaffolds was investigated in short-term cultivation studies of murine osteosarcoma cells K7M2-wt seeded onto the scaffolds. The scaffolds were cultivated in perfusion bioreactors at the superficial flow velocity of 15 $\mu\text{m/s}$, while static cultures served as a control. After cultivation, osteosarcoma cells remained adhered to the scaffold surface, expressed metabolic activity and retained their initial proliferation ability while the flow was shown to positively affect the cultivated cells.